

AUTOMATION AND HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT IN THE NIGERIAN OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

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Abstract: This study examined the impact of automation on human capital development within the Nigerian oil and gas industry. It specifically focused on the potential for reskilling and upskilling and the adaptability of the workforce to automation-driven changes. The study employed a descriptive survey research design, utilizing a questionnaire to collect data from a sample of 385 workers, selected from a population of 10,671 employees across three major oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The sample was determined using the Yamane Taro method, and a multi-stage sampling technique was employed to target industry experts. The findings indicate a generally positive perception of reskilling and upskilling opportunities, with an overall mean score of 4.02, which suggest that the industry is making significant efforts to equip its workforce with the necessary skills to handle automation. However, some variability in responses highlights the need for improved accessibility and structure of these programs. Regarding workforce adaptability to automation-driven changes, the overall mean score of 4.14 reflects a strong capacity to adapt, though the data reveals challenges in training effectiveness, managerial support, and the pace of technological advancements. The study concluded that while the Nigerian oil and gas industry is proactive in addressing the challenges posed by automation through reskilling and upskilling initiatives, there are areas for improvement, particularly in ensuring equitable access to these programs and enhancing support mechanisms for workers. These efforts are critical for sustaining the growth of the industry and ensuring that the workforce can fully leverage the benefits of automation.

Keywords: capital development, automation, Nigerian oil and gas industry, challenges.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian oil and gas industry, a critical driver of the nation's economy, is undergoing significant transformations due to advancements in automation technologies. As global energy demands evolve, companies, in the sector increasingly adopt automation to enhance efficiency, reduce operational costs, and improve safety standards [1], [2]. This shift which offers substantial economic benefits presents a complex challenge for the

workforce. Automation technologies, including robotics, artificial intelligence (AI), and machine learning, are poised to reshape job roles. According to Benanav [3], automation will potentially render certain manual and routine tasks obsolete while creating new opportunities for highly skilled labour. This paradigm shift necessitates a focused examination of human capital development, particularly in terms of reskilling and upskilling the existing workforce to align with the industry's evolving needs.

Reskilling and upskilling are critical components of human capital development in that they enable workers to acquire new competencies and adapt to technological advancements [4]. In the context of the Nigerian oil and gas industry, the urgency of these strategies cannot be overstated. As automation increasingly penetrates the industry, there is a growing need for a workforce that is not only technically proficient but also adaptable to rapid technological changes. Previous studies in similar sectors globally have highlighted the potential of targeted reskilling programs to mitigate the displacement of workers by automation. There is a strong emphasis on the importance of aligning training programs with the specific demands of the industry [5]. In Nigeria, however, the implementation of such programs faces unique challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, limited access to quality education, and socio-economic factors that may hinder the effectiveness of these initiatives.

Moreover, the adaptability of the Nigerian workforce to automation-driven changes is a critical area of concern. The ability of workers to transition from traditional roles to more technologically advanced positions is influenced by several factors, including educational background, access to continuous professional development, and the support provided by industry stakeholders. Studies have shown that in regions where the workforce is better educated and has greater access to training opportunities, the adaptability to automation is significantly higher [6]. However, in the Nigerian context, where there is a disparity in access to quality education and professional development resources, there may be substantial barriers to workforce adaptability. Additionally, the cultural and organizational readiness for change within the industry plays a significant role in shaping the adaptability of the workforce to new technologies.

The intersection of automation and human capital development in the Nigerian oil and gas industry is further complicated by the broader socio-economic settings. The Nigerian economy is heavily reliant on the oil and gas sector. However, the sector has faced pressures from fluctuating oil prices, regulatory uncertainties, and a growing demand for more sustainable energy practices [7]. These factors, combined with the rapid pace of technological change, create a complex environment in which the workforce must navigate. The role of government in facilitating this transition through policy support, investment in education and training, and fostering public-private partnerships is important to ensuring that the benefits of automation are equitably distributed across the workforce.

Furthermore, the global trend towards energy transition, driven by environmental concerns and the push for cleaner energy sources, adds another layer of complexity to human capital development in Nigeria's oil and gas industry. As companies diversify their energy portfolios to include renewable sources, the skills required within the industry are also changing. This shift necessitates not only technical skills but also an understanding of sustainable practices and the ability to work with new energy technologies. For the Nigerian workforce, this means

that reskilling and upskilling efforts must be forward-looking. Workers are not only prepared for the immediate challenges posed by automation but also for the long-term transition to a more diversified energy landscape. Given the unique challenges and opportunities within the Nigerian context, this study aims to contribute to the understanding of how automation can be harnessed to drive human capital development in a way that supports the long-term growth and sustainability of the oil and gas industry.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Armrah [8] in a study titled "Automation in the oil and gas industry" carried out an investigation into the automation process in the oil and gas industry. The study adopted literature review as a methodology to explore development in this area. The three segments of oil and gas industry were first investigated. Technology's effect on this field was then explored. In addition, this study investigates current automation technology. The challenges and requirements are detected for automation and robotics in this area. Future research opportunities were also explored. The study showed that the oil and gas industry will benefit immensely from automation, and that the workforce will stand to gain from automation too. According to the author the health and safety and environmental (HSE) aspect of the industry will improve tremendously. Thus, the workforce may likely find satisfaction in increased safety in the oil and gas industry.

Morandini *et al.* [9] conducted a study titled "The impact of artificial intelligence on workers' skills: Upskilling and reskilling in organizations," which aimed to investigate recent developments in research and practice concerning the transformation of professional skills by artificial intelligence (AI) and to identify solutions to the challenges that arise. The authors conducted a narrative review to analyse research and practice on the impact of AI on human skills in organizations. The study revealed that introducing AI in organizations involves multiple organizational strategies. Firstly, it is crucial to identify the transversal skills needed by workers to address the current skills gap within the workplace. Secondly, organizations can assist workers in identifying the skills required for AI adoption, enhancing existing skills, and developing new ones. Additionally, the findings emphasize the importance of implementing processes to support workers by providing tailored training and development opportunities, ensuring that workers' attitudes and mental models towards AI are open and adaptable to the evolving labour market and its associated challenges.

Wanasinghe *et al.* [10], in their study titled "Human centric digital transformation and operator 4.0 for the oil and gas industry," highlighted the potential of leveraging emerging digital technologies such as smart sensors, wearable or mobile devices, big data analytics, cloud computing, extended reality technologies, robotic systems, and drones to address challenges encountered by oil and gas workers. However, the authors pointed out that while these technologies are not new to the industry, most existing digital transformation initiatives focus on business or process-centric approaches, prioritizing enhancements in production efficiency and revenue generation. Consequently, these initiatives may overlook the challenges faced by workers. Recognizing oil and gas workers as essential assets in the industry, the authors emphasized the importance of addressing their challenges. To this end, the study proposed a human-centric digital transformational framework for the oil and gas sector, aiming to deploy existing digital technologies to improve workers' health, safety, and working conditions.

Roberts and Flin [11] conducted a study titled "Unlocking the potential: Understanding the psychological factors that influence technology adoption in the upstream oil and gas industry," which aimed to shed light on the psychological factors influencing the acceptance and deployment of innovative technology in the industry. The authors highlighted the need to better understand these factors to maximize the opportunities for adopting newly developed products. They noted the scarcity of research specifically addressing psychological factors in the upstream energy sector, despite extensive literature on consumer behaviour and technology use in general. Through a literature review, the study aimed to identify existing research on psychological factors influencing technology adoption in the oil and gas industry and interventions designed to support such adoption. The findings revealed five key psychological factors: personality traits (e.g., exploration traits, risk aversion), attitudes (e.g., trust, not-invented-here syndrome), social factors (e.g., social norms), cognitive factors (e.g., risk perception), and organizational-level psychological factors (e.g., leadership, organizational culture). Additionally, the review identified a limited number of interventions developed to facilitate technology adoption in the oil and gas industry. Wanasinghe *et al.* [12] conducted a study titled "Digitalization and the future of employment: A case study on the Canadian offshore oil and gas drilling occupations," which introduced a novel approach to predicting the transformation of offshore oil and gas drilling jobs amidst the fourth industrial revolution (Industry 4.0). The study proposed an algorithm focused on identifying reskilling requirements, job merging pathways, and a tentative time-line for this transformation. This algorithm introduced a scaling factor called digital readiness level, which considers various factors such as the cost of technology development, labour market dynamics, economic benefits, regulatory readiness, and social acceptance. A feature-based approach was developed to assess similarities between occupations, while a mathematical model was created to project automation trajectories for each job under investigation. These tools enabled the consideration of potential job merging scenarios and associated time-lines. The study's findings projected a significant reduction in the total number of personnel on board (POB) in offshore drilling platforms to six by 2058. The study concluded that the optimal benefits of digital transformation initiatives could only be achieved if technology adoption aligns with workforce reformation. Additionally, it emphasized that human capital investments might not yield substantial benefits if technology adoption and workforce reformation occur at different rates.

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study employed a descriptive survey research design. As highlighted by author [13], research design is a critical component of any research. It provides the framework and structure for how the research is conducted. The decision to use a descriptive research approach in this study, aimed at appraise automation and human capital development in the Nigeria's oil and gas industry, was driven by several key factors. Descriptive research involves gathering data that can be statistically analysed, enabling the identification of correlations and trends within large datasets [14]. This approach is particularly well-suited to address the research questions of this study due to its ability to produce precise and reliable results through systematic data collection and analysis.

3.2 Area of Study

The study was conducted in Niger Delta region of Nigeria, which is home to the majority of the oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The Niger Delta is the delta of the Niger River, situated along the Gulf of Guinea on the Atlantic Ocean. The region spans approximately 70,000 square kilometres, accounting for about 7.5% of Nigeria's land area. It is home to roughly 31 million people. The Niger Delta generates over 90% of Nigeria's oil and gas revenue, contributes 80% of the GDP, and supports 95% of the national budget [15]. Given the concentration of oil and gas activities in this area, the study deems it essential to investigate the impact of automation on the Nigerian oil and gas industry in the area. No other part of Nigeria has such a significant presence of oil and gas companies. The Niger Delta was the site of Nigeria's first oil exploration and has remained the focal point of oil and gas activities in Nigeria ever since.

3.3 Determination of Sample Size

The study encompass a population of 10,671 staff members from the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation Limited (NNPCL), Chevron, and Total Energy, Nigeria PLC. The Taro Yamane formula, expressed as Equation 3.1, was utilized to determine the sample size for this study:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \quad (3.1)$$

where,

n = sample size

N = total population under study

e = error limit (an error limit of 0.05 was used for the study).

Applying this formula to the population of 10671; yielded a sample size of 385. A multi stage sampling technique was used to sample the appropriate numbers of staffers from each of the three oil companies. To allocate the sample size proportionally to each oil and gas company under study, Burley's proportional allocation formula was employed. The formula is stated thus;

$$n_b = \frac{n(h)}{N} \quad (3.2)$$

where

n_b = Sample proportion allocated to a given group

n = Total sample size

h = Population of a specific group

N = Population of the study

Table 3.1: Proportion allocation of a sample size to the oil and gas companies

Oil and Gas Company	Population	Sample size (n_b)
NNPCL	6621	239
Chevron	2400	87
Total Nigeria PLC	1650	59
Total	10671	385

The information available in Table 3.1 shows that a total of 239 staffers were sampled from Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation Limited (NNPCL), 87 from Chevron, and 59 from Total Nigeria PLC. The second stage involved expert sampling. The sampling specifically targeted expert that are in automated sector of the companies.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results depicting the potential for reskilling and upskilling of the workforce in response to automation in the Nigerian oil and gas industry is presented in Table 4.1, while Figure 4.1 shows the trend of this potentials.

Table 4.1: The potential for reskilling and upskilling of the workforce in response to automation in the Nigerian oil and gas industry.

S/N	Item Symbol	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Undecided (U)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Total	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	A	184 (48.4%)	100 (26.3%)	46 (12.1%)	36 (9.5%)	14 (3.7%)	380 (100%)	4.06	1.15
2	B	148 (38.9%)	163 (42.9%)	20 (5.3%)	15 (3.9%)	34 (8.9%)	380 (100%)	3.99	1.59
3	C	261 (68.7%)	84 (22.1%)	12 (3.2%)	14 (3.7%)	9 (2.4%)	380 (100%)	4.51	0.91
4	D	281 (73.9%)	74 (19.5%)	5 (1.3%)	9 (2.4%)	11 (2.9%)	380 (100%)	4.59	0.87
5	E	297 (78.2%)	66 (17.4%)	4 (1.1%)	5 (1.3%)	8 (2.1%)	380 (100%)	4.68	0.76
6	F	147 (38.7%)	98 (25.8%)	57 (15.0%)	31 (8.2%)	47 (12.4%)	380 (100%)	3.70	1.38
7	G	171 (45.0%)	103 (27.1%)	21 (5.5%)	44 (11.6%)	41 (10.8%)	380 (100%)	3.84	1.39
8	H	102 (26.8%)	89 (23.4%)	43 (11.3%)	87 (22.9%)	59 (15.2%)	380 (100%)	3.23	1.45
9	I	169 (44.5%)	107 (28.2%)	15 (3.9%)	31 (8.2%)	58 (15.3%)	380 (100%)	3.78	1.46

S/N	Item Symbol	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Undecided (U)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Total	Mean	Standard Deviation
10	J	69 (18.2%)	91 (23.9%)	112 (29.5%)	46 (12.1%)	62 (16.3%)	380 (100%)	3.16	1.31
11	K	214 (56.3%)	103 (27.1%)	7 (1.8%)	32 (8.4%)	24 (6.3%)	380 (100%)	4.19	1.21
12	L	274 (72.1%)	69 (18.2%)	4 (1.1%)	19 (5.0%)	14 (3.7%)	380 (100)	4.50	1.01
OVERALL MEAN/ STANDARD DEVIATION								4.02	1.23

Description of item symbols:

A = There are ample opportunities for reskilling in response to automation in the Nigerian oil and gas industry.

B = Upskilling programs are widely available to employees affected by automation in the Nigerian oil and gas sector, C = Training programs for new automated technologies are effectively provided in the Nigerian oil and gas industry, D = The Nigerian oil and gas industry supports continuous learning and development for automation-related skills, E = Employees are encouraged to participate in reskilling programs due to automation changes in the industry, F = There is a clear pathway for career advancement through upskilling in response to automation in the industry,

G = Adequate resources are allocated for workforce reskilling in the Nigerian oil and gas industry,

H = Collaboration with educational institutions for upskilling and reskilling programs is strong in the industry,

I = The Nigerian oil and gas industry provides incentives for employees to engage in upskilling activities,

J = Reskilling initiatives are well-structured and accessible to all employees in the industry,

K = The workforce is open and receptive to reskilling and upskilling opportunities provided by the industry,

L = Automation has positively influenced the culture of continuous improvement and skill enhancement in the industry.

Figure 4.1: The potential for reskilling and upskilling of the workforce in response to automation in the Nigerian oil and gas industry

The data from the Nigerian oil and gas industry provides critical insights into the readiness of the workforce for reskilling and upskilling in response to automation. A substantial portion of the workforce recognizes the availability of reskilling opportunities, with 48.4% strongly agreeing and 26.3% agreeing, resulting in a mean score of 4.06. This suggests that nearly three-quarters of the respondents view the industry as providing ample opportunities for acquiring new skills, though a mean standard deviation of 1.15 indicates some variation in these perceptions. Similarly, upskilling programs, which are essential for adapting to automation-driven changes, are perceived positively by 38.9% of respondents who strongly agree and 42.9% who agree, leading to a mean score of 3.99. However, the higher standard deviation of 1.59 suggests variability in the effectiveness or accessibility of these programs across different workforce segments. Training programs specifically designed for new automated technologies are particularly effective, with a significant 68.7% of respondents strongly agreeing, resulting in one of the highest mean scores at 4.51. The low standard deviation of 0.91 associated with this item indicates a strong consensus among respondents.

Moreover, the support for continuous learning and development within the industry is widely acknowledged, as 73.9% of respondents strongly agree that the industry fosters such an environment, yielding a high mean score of 4.59. The low standard deviation of 0.87 further underscores the widespread agreement on the commitment of the industry to ongoing professional development, which is crucial for maintaining a competitive and skilled workforce in an increasingly automated environment. In contrast, the perception of clear career advancement pathways through upskilling shows more variability, with 38.7% strongly agreeing but 12.4% strongly

disagreeing, leading to a lower mean score of 3.70 and a higher standard deviation of 1.38. This suggests that while some employees see clear benefits from upskilling, others may not perceive these opportunities as accessible or effective for career progression. Additionally, the allocation of resources for reskilling is perceived as adequate by 45.0% of respondents, reflected in a mean score of 3.84. However, the higher standard deviation of 1.39 indicates that there may be disparities in how these resources are distributed or perceived. Collaboration with educational institutions for upskilling and reskilling programs is an area where perceptions are notably mixed. While 26.8% of respondents strongly agree that such collaborations are strong, a significant 15.2% strongly disagree, resulting in a lower mean score of 3.23 and a standard deviation of 1.45. This suggests a need for stronger partnerships between the industry and educational institutions to ensure that training programs are up-to-date and aligned with industry needs.

Incentives for engaging in upskilling activities are viewed favorably by 44.5% of respondents, resulting in a mean score of 3.78, although the relatively high standard deviation of 1.46 suggests that these incentives may not be uniformly recognized or valued across the workforce. The accessibility and structure of reskilling initiatives receive a more critical assessment, with only 18.2% strongly agreeing on their accessibility, leading to the lowest mean score of 3.16 and a standard deviation of 1.31. This indicates potential challenges in the structure or communication of these opportunities, which could limit their effectiveness. Despite these challenges, there is a strong openness among the workforce toward reskilling and upskilling, with 56.3% strongly agreeing on their willingness to participate in such programs, reflected in a mean score of 4.19. This positive attitude is crucial for the successful implementation of workforce development initiatives. Additionally, the perception that automation has positively influenced the culture of continuous improvement and skill enhancement is strong, with 72.1% of respondents strongly agreeing, yielding a high mean score of 4.50 and a standard deviation of 1.01.

Generally, the Nigerian oil and gas industry demonstrates a strong commitment to supporting its workforce through reskilling and upskilling in response to automation. However, the data indicates areas for improvement, particularly in enhancing the structure and accessibility of these programs, strengthening external collaborations, and ensuring equitable distribution of resources and incentives. There is a need to address these issues to fully harness the potential of automation for sustainable growth within the industry.

Table 4.2: Adaptability of workforce in the Nigerian oil and gas industry to automation-driven changes in the industry.

S/N	Item Symbol	Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Undecided (U)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Total	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	A	163 (42.9%)	97 (25.5%)	17 (4.5%)	54 (14.2%)	49 (12.9%)	380 100%	3.71	1.46
2	B	147 (38.7%)	103 (27.1%)	8 (2.1%)	65 (17.1%)	57 (15.0%)	380 (100%)	3.57	1.51
3	C	287 (75.5%)	63 (16.6%)	5 (1.3%)	4 (1.1%)	21 (5.5%)	380 (100%)	4.56	1.00
4	D	269 (70.8%)	77 (20.3%)	3 (0.8%)	12 (3.2%)	19 (5.0%)	380 (100%)	4.49	1.03
5	E	232 (61.1%)	81 (21.3%)	17 (4.5%)	21 (5.5%)	29 (7.6%)	380 (100%)	4.23	1.23
6	F	154 (40.5%)	129 (33.9%)	31 (8.2%)	36 (9.5%)	30 (7.9%)	380 (100%)	3.90	1.25
7	G	279 (73.4%)	49 (12.9%)	5 (1.3%)	21 (5.5%)	26 (6.8%)	380 (100%)	4.41	1.19
8	H	201 (52.9%)	63 (16.6%)	12 (3.2%)	47 (12.4%)	57 (15.0%)	380 (100%)	3.80	1.54
9	I	102 (26.8%)	156 (41.1%)	7 (1.8%)	54 (14.2%)	61 (16.1%)	380 (100%)	3.48	1.43
10	J	282 (74.2%)	74 (19.5%)	5 (1.3%)	11 (2.9%)	8 (2.1%)	380 (100%)	4.61	0.83
11	K	284 (74.7%)	67 (17.6%)	5 (1.3%)	10 (2.6%)	14 (3.7%)	380 (100%)	4.57	0.93
12	L	251 (66.1%)	61 (16.1%)	18 (4.7%)	26 (6.81%)	24 (6.3%)	380 (100%)	4.29	1.21
OVERALL MEAN/ STANDARD DEVIATION								4.14	1.24

Description of symbols:

A = Workers in the Nigerian oil and gas industry are well-prepared to handle automation-driven changes,

B = Training programs are effective in helping workers adapt to new automated technologies,

C = Automation has improved the efficiency of operations in the oil and gas industry,

- D = Workers are confident in their ability to learn and use new automated systems,
- E = The introduction of automation has led to significant changes in job roles and responsibilities,
- F = There is adequate support from management for workers transitioning to automated systems,
- G = Automation has resulted in job displacement in the oil and gas industry,
- H = Workers have access to continuous learning opportunities to keep up with automation trends,
- I = The implementation of automation has increased job satisfaction among workers,
- J = Automation-driven changes have improved safety standards in the oil and gas industry,
- K = Workers face challenges in adapting to the pace of technological advancements in automation,
- L = The skills required for automated systems are adequately addressed in the current training programs.

Figure 4.2: Adaptability of workforce in the Nigerian oil and gas industry to automation-driven changes in the industry.

The data on how workers in the Nigerian oil and gas industry adapt to automation-driven changes reveals a diverse range of experiences and perceptions. The overall mean score of 4.14 with a standard deviation of 1.24 indicates a generally positive adaptation process, though with notable variations in specific areas. A significant portion of the workforce, 42.9% of respondents, believe they are well-prepared to handle automation-driven changes, yielding a mean score of 3.71. However, the higher standard deviation of 1.46 suggests that while many workers feel prepared, there is considerable variation in confidence levels across the industry. This may reflect differences in access to resources, training, or support. Training programs, which are essential for facilitating adaptation to new automated technologies, are viewed somewhat positively, with 38.7% of respondents agreeing on their

effectiveness, resulting in a mean score of 3.57. However, the standard deviation of 1.51 indicates mixed perceptions, possibly due to variations in the quality or relevance of these programs. This suggests that while training is available, it may not consistently meet the needs of all workers. The impact of automation on operational efficiency is overwhelmingly positive, with 75.5% of respondents agreeing that it has improved efficiency, reflected in a high mean score of 4.56 and a relatively low standard deviation of 1.00. This consensus highlights the tangible benefits of automation in enhancing productivity within the industry.

Moreover, the confidence of workers in their ability to learn and use new automated systems is also high, with 70.8% strongly agreeing, leading to a mean score of 4.49 and a standard deviation of 1.03. This suggests a strong sense of capability among the workforce, which is imperative for successful adaptation to automation-driven changes. The introduction of automation has significantly altered job roles and responsibilities, with 61.1% of respondents acknowledging these changes, resulting in a mean score of 4.23 and a standard deviation of 1.23. This shift underscores the transformational impact of automation on the nature of work in the industry, necessitating ongoing adaptation and skill development. Support from management is perceived as adequate by 40.5% of respondents, contributing to a mean score of 3.90. However, a standard deviation of 1.25 indicates that while some workers feel supported, others may experience gaps in managerial support during the transition to automated systems. The perception that automation has led to job displacement is strong, with 73.4% of respondents agreeing, resulting in a mean score of 4.41 and a standard deviation of 1.19. This highlights a critical concern within the workforce, reflecting the disruptive potential of automation on employment in the industry.

Furthermore, access to continuous learning opportunities, essential for keeping pace with automation trends, is viewed positively by 52.9% of respondents, leading to a mean score of 3.80. However, the high standard deviation of 1.54 suggests significant disparities in access to these opportunities, which could hinder the ability of some workers to adapt. The effect of automation on job satisfaction is more mixed, with a mean score of 3.48 and a standard deviation of 1.43, indicating that while some workers may experience increased satisfaction, others may not, potentially due to the pressures and uncertainties associated with technological change.

Automation-driven changes are seen as improving safety standards in the industry, with 74.2% of respondents agreeing, resulting in the highest mean score of 4.61 and a low standard deviation of 0.83. This strong agreement underscores the critical role of automation in enhancing safety, a key priority in the oil and gas sector.

Nevertheless, challenges in adapting to the pace of technological advancements are acknowledged by 74.7% of respondents, leading to a mean score of 4.57 and a standard deviation of 0.93. This indicates that while workers recognize the benefits of automation, the rapid pace of change poses significant adaptation challenges. Lastly, the adequacy of current training programs in addressing the skills required for automated systems is affirmed by 66.1% of respondents, with a mean score of 4.29 and a standard deviation of 1.21. This suggests that while training is generally effective, there may be room for improvement in ensuring that programs fully align with the demands of new technologies. In a nutshell, the Nigerian oil and gas workforce demonstrates a strong capacity to adapt to automation-driven changes, the data indicates areas for enhancement, particularly in training effectiveness,

managerial support, and access to continuous learning opportunities. These areas are critical for ensuring that the workforce can fully leverage the benefits of automation while mitigating its disruptive effects.

V. CONCLUSION

This study has comprehensively appraised automation and human capital development in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. It has been shown in the study that the potential for reskilling and upskilling in response to automation in the Nigeria's oil and gas industry is substantial. The industry offers numerous opportunities for employees to develop new competencies. This is achieved through effective training programs, incentives, and collaborations with educational institutions. This robust support framework indicates a proactive approach by the industry to equip its workforce with the necessary skills to thrive in an automated environment. Lastly, the study shows that workers in the Nigerian oil and gas industry exhibit a strong ability to adapt to automation-driven changes. The workers demonstrate confidence in learning new technologies and adapting to new roles. This adaptability is imperative for the successful integration of automation in the industry. Evidently, it ensures that the workforce remains competent and competitive.

Conclusively, the study examines the significant yet intricate role of automation in transforming the Nigerian oil and gas industry. While automation offers numerous advantages, including enhanced efficiency, increased job satisfaction, and skill development, it also introduces challenges that necessitate strategic management. These challenges primarily involve the need for reskilling, upskilling, and ensuring job security. The industry's proactive approach to addressing these issues suggests a promising future.

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